

Scaling-up Of A Highly Modular Rotating Packed Bed Plant With An Efficient Solvent For Capture Cost Reduction: An Overview of the HiRECORD Project

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In a world's first, HiRECORD will demonstrate at TRL 6, a modular CO₂ capture plant that will comprise a Rotating Packed Bed (RPB) absorber and an advanced RPB desorber with integrated spinning reboiler (RPB-ISR). The plant will be of 10 t/d CO₂ capture capacity and will operate with the advanced, APBS-CDRMax solvent. It will be operated on the premises of a natural-gas power plant, of an industrial gas boiler and of a quicklime plant, highlighting the high modularity and flexibility of RPB processes with flue gases of different specifications. Studies will also take place, pertaining to the solvent operation and equipment corrosion under the influence of contaminants such as SO_x and NO_x. Solvent modeling under such contaminants will be based on the SAFT- γ Mie equation of state. The advanced capture plant will allow up to 50% capture cost reduction, compared to conventional MEA-based, packed-bed technologies. This reduction will result from at least 10 times lower space footprint due to the use of the RPBs, with direct beneficial impacts on capital expenditures, as well as a regeneration energy of 2.1 GJ/tCO₂ due to the use of the APBS-CDRMax solvent and the RPB-ISR. These features will also enable 20% and 50% lower environmental and safety impacts, as the solvent and operating conditions will minimize emissions, corrosion and make-up requirements. Techno-economic studies will also include an industrial cluster in Northern Greece, where options of CO₂ utilization as well transportation and

sequestration in nearby geological sites will also be investigated. Extensive societal, public acceptance and policy studies will also be performed.

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